

ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ДИПЛОМАТИЯ ТАДЖИКИСТАНА: ПОДХОД К ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ

Курбонов Маъруф Муидинович

младший сотрудник Научно-исследовательского института зеленой экономики
Государственного учреждения «Международного университета туризма и
предпринимательства Таджикистана

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Аннотация. В данной статье изучается роль Республики Таджикистан в развитии зеленой дипломатии, а также её вклад в экологическую безопасность и устойчивое развитие региона. Приоритетное направление уделяется водной дипломатии, как одному из ключевых аспектов внешней политики страны, и её вкладу в решение климатических проблем Центральной Азии.

Ключевые слова: зеленая дипломатия, водная дипломатия, Республика Таджикистан, экологическая безопасность, устойчивое развитие, страны региона, Центральная Азия, шёлковый путь.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola Tojikiston Respublikasining yashil diplomatiyani rivojlantirishdagi roli, shuningdek, uning ekologik xavfsizlik va mintaqaning barqaror rivojlanishiga qo'shgan hissasi ko'rib chiqiladi. Mamlakat tashqi siyosatining asosiy yo'nalishlaridan biri sifatida suv diplomatiyasiga, uning Markaziy Osiyodagi iqlim muammolarini hal etishga qo'shgan hissasiga ustuvor ahamiyat beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: yashil diplomatiya, suv diplomatiyasi, Tojikiston Respublikasi, ekologik xavfsizlik, barqaror rivojlanish, mintaqqa mamlakatlari, Markaziy Osiyo, ishqoriy yo'l.

Abstract. This article examines the role of the Republic of Tajikistan in the development of green diplomacy, as well as its contribution to environmental security and sustainable development of the region. Priority is given to water diplomacy, as one of the key aspects of the country's foreign policy, and its contribution to solving the climate problems of Central Asia.

Keywords: green diplomacy, water diplomacy, the Republic of Tajikistan, environmental security, sustainable development, countries of the region, Central Asia, alkali route.

Tajikistan's green diplomacy is an integral part of global directions to ensure environmental security and sustainable development. Tajikistan, which has extensive water resources, plays an important role in Central Asia, and its environmental policy is aimed at solving global climate problems. The President of Tajikistan Emomali Rahmon has repeatedly emphasized the importance of rational use of water resources: “Together, we have been able to put water at the centre of global development negotiations and unite the global community around this extremely important topic.” [3]

An important area of Tajikistan's green diplomacy is water diplomacy. As a country that owns more than 60% of Central Asia's water resources, Tajikistan bears significant responsibility for the rational use of this wealth in the interests of the region. As Emomali Rahmon noted: “Water is not just a resource, it is a factor of stability and cooperation.” This approach is confirmed by Tajikistan's active participation in international environmental initiatives, such as the UN Decade of Action on Water (2018–2028).

Tajikistan actively supports the concepts of green diplomacy and sustainable development in the international arena, including UN events, interacting with numerous global organizations. Former UN Secretary-General Ban Ki-moon in one of his speeches emphasized the leading role

of Tajikistan in water resources management: "Tajikistan continues to demonstrate an example of a responsible approach to water resources, which contributes to the solution of global environmental problems." [1]

Tajikistan's green diplomacy also aims to introduce green technologies and sustainable methods of using natural resources. These initiatives are important for mitigating the impact of climate change and addressing environmental challenges such as drought and land degradation. Paul Hawkin, a renowned environmentalist, said: "Green technologies are not just a trend, they are our way to preserving the planet." [2]

In the context of environmental challenges in Central Asia, including climate change, droughts and deterioration of ecosystems, Tajikistan's green diplomacy is aimed at strengthening interaction between the countries of the region to ensure collective environmental security. These efforts are supported by sustainable development strategies and innovative methods of natural resource management, which confirms the significant role of Tajikistan in global environmental policy.

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